

Supplementary Appendix 16.1. Response of alien plants to fire or grazing management in long-term rangeland experiments or long-standing fence-line contrasts (FLC; fence lines often separate land parcels subjected to different management practices and stocking rates, and offer opportunities for comparison of outcomes)

Location, coordinates	Biome, mean annual rainfall, altitude (asl)	Description of treatments	Description of invasive alien species	Source
Cathedral Peak 28°59'S; 29°14'E	Grassland, 1400-1700 mm, 1850-2210 m	Catchment experiment of fire-return interval (1-8 years)	Sparse <i>Oenothera rosea</i> on 2 seeps; no alien plants on 35 dryland plots	Gordijn et al. 2018
Cathedral Peak 28°59'S; 29°16'E	Grassland, 1700 mm, 1840-2000 m	Fire exclusion (accidental fires) in catchment IX, 1952-current	No woody aliens recorded in 1973 or in 1986, scattered mature <i>Pinus patula</i> present in 2010	Granger 1976; Adcock 1990; T.G. O'Connor, pers. obs.
Cathedral Peak 29°00'S; 29°15'E	Grassland, 1380 mm, 1890 m	Brotherton trial: frequency and season of burning	Dense (40% cover) <i>Rubus cuneifolius</i> on fire-protected and octennial burning treatments but none on plots with fire-return intervals <8 years	P. Gordijn, SAEON, unpublished data
Athole 26°32'S; 30°32'E	Grassland, 992 mm, 1483 m	Exclusion of fire and grazing on a N (1 fire) and S aspect, 1954-1999	<i>Acacia mearnsii</i> (dominant) and 1 herb species established on moist S aspect; shrub <i>R. cuneifolius</i> (18% cover) on N aspect; none on adjacent burnt grassland	Titshall et al. 2001
Athole 26°32'S; 30°32'E	Grassland, 992 mm, 1620 m	Period of deferment before stocking sheep on spring-burnt sourveld, 992-1997	No herbaceous or woody alien species	Kirkman 1999; pers. comm.
nThabamhlope 29°01'S; 29°39'E	Grassland, 800 mm, 1510 m	Exclusion of fire and grazing on N aspect, 1939-1992, 2 burns by 2010	Sparse amounts of 5 alien forb species in 1983; 15 m ² clump of <i>A. mearnsii</i> by 2010; none on adjacent burnt grassland	Westfall et al. 1983; T.G. O'Connor, unpublished data
Kokstad 30°31'S; 29°21'E	Grassland, 790 mm, 1340-1560 m	3 trials: stocking rate of sheep on hill slope or on flat; stocking rate by cattle-to-sheep ratio	A few individuals of the herbs <i>Verbena brasiliensis</i> , <i>Conyza</i> sp., <i>Hypochoeris radicata</i> , <i>Plantago virginica</i>	O'Connor et al. 2011

Döhne 32°31'S; 27°25'	Grassland, 762 mm, 899 m	Exclusion of fire and grazing on a N (1 fire) and S aspect (2 fires), 1964-1999	Woody species (individuals ha ⁻¹): <i>A. mearnsii</i> (0.5) on N, (12) on S aspect; <i>Eucalyptus</i> sp. (1) and <i>Pinus pinaster</i> seedlings on N aspect; <i>Richardia brasiliensis</i> 11-18% cover, 1 other alien herb species; none on adjacent grassland	Titshall et al. 2001
Ermelo 26°32'S; 29°58'E	Grassland, 719 mm, 1694 m	Rest regimes under sheep grazing, 1993-1997	No herbaceous or woody alien species	Kirkman 1999; pers. comm.
Ukulinga 29°40'S; 30°24'E	Grassland, 694 mm, 840 m	a. Exclusion of fire and grazing, 1950-1999 b. Annual and triennial burning, fire exclusion, 1950-current	a. Woody species (individuals ha ⁻¹): <i>A. mearnsii</i> (53), <i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i> (13), <i>Lantana camara</i> (92), <i>Melia azedarach</i> (240); none on adjacent grassland b. Fire exclusion promoted 2 herbaceous alien species; none on adjacent grassland	a. Titshall et al. 2001 b. Kirkman et al. 2014
Kruger National Park 25°10'S, 31°16'E; 25°7'S, 31°29'E; 24°24'S, 31°47'E; 23°32'S, 31°24'E	Savanna 737, 550, 537 and 447 mm; 580, 400, 270 and 320 m	Trial of frequency and season of burning including complete protection, 4 vegetation types, 1954-current	Woody species: 3 <i>L. camara</i> plants in the protected and 1 in the triennial February (cool burn) <i>Terminalia</i> (high rainfall) plots by 2016 but not in the 1990s; none in the plots with a short fire-return interval	Biggs et al. 2003; SANParks unpubl. data
Towoomba 24°25'S; 28°21'E	Savanna, 627 mm, 1184 m	Exclusion of fire and grazing, 1934-2000	<i>L. camara</i> , increased from 0 to 242 individuals ha ⁻¹ , 1977-2000 (4.8% of woody individuals)	Jordaan 2010
Mopani 22°14'S; 29°55'E	Savanna, 342 mm, 559 m	Exclusion of herbivory and fire, 1965-2001	No alien woody or grass species, herbaceous species not reported.	Jordaan et al. 2004
Southern Kalahari 26°56'S; 21°08'E	Savanna, 180 mm, 895 m	FLC of 6.5 ha vs 25 ha per LSU	No alien species	Rutherford and Powrie 2009
Sundays River Valley 33°33'S, 25°28'E; 33°14'S, 24°53'E	Albany Thicket, 381 and 294 mm, 300 and 550 m	FLC of stocking rate (>10 years) under commercial grazing	No alien species	Hoffman and Cowling 1990
Ikwezi district 33°13'S; 25°02'E	Albany Thicket, 273 mm, 600 m	FLC of 0.05 (LU) vs 0.09 (HU) LSU ha ⁻¹ (goats and sheep) over decades	Frequency (%) for LU vs HU: <i>A. lindleyi</i> 0 to 31; <i>Chenopodium murale</i> 0 to 9; <i>Portulaca oleracea</i> 0 to 6 (all significant)	Rutherford et al. 2014

Grootfontein 31°29'S; 25°01'E	Nama-Karoo, 372 mm, 1264 m	a. Season of sheep grazing, 1946-2010 b. Season and system of sheep grazing, 1949-1971, residual effects in 2010	No response to treatment evident, with odd individuals of the herbs <i>Argemone mexicana</i> , <i>Chenopodium glaucum</i> , <i>Erigeron filifolius</i> and <i>Salsola kali</i> , the grass <i>Paspalum dilitatum</i> , and scattered <i>Salvia verbenaca</i>	a. Du Toit et al. 2018; pers. comm. b. O'Connor and Roux (1995); J. Du Toit unpubl. data
Sundays River Valley 33°06'S; 24°18'E	Nama-Karoo, 230 mm, 600 m	FLC of stocking rate (>10 years) under commercial grazing	No alien species	Hoffman and Cowling 1990
Carnarvon 30°58'S; 21°58'E	Nama-Karoo, 215 mm, 1300 m	Sheep stocking rate experiment conducted from 1988 to 2015	No response to treatment evident, with odd individuals of the herbs <i>Chenopodium album</i> , <i>Lepidium</i> sp., and <i>Medicago sativa</i>	van der Merwe et al. 2018
Tierberg 33°10'S; 22°17'E	Succulent Karoo, 175 mm, 800 m	a. FLC of grazing intensity over 20 years b. N-fertilisation, 20 years c. 1 burn assessed 8 years later	Sparse <i>Atriplex inflata</i> , promoted by N addition and possibly by grazing intensity; no aliens evident after burning	a. Seymour et al. 2010; pers comm. b. Seymour and Milton (pers. comm.) c. van der Merwe et al. 2016
Hoekdoorn 33°S; 19.8°E	Succulent Karoo, 110 mm, 575 m	FLC of 4 vs 7-10 ha per small stock unit for decades	1 <i>S. kali</i> plant	Rutherford and Powrie 2010

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